

INVESTIGATION OF A MODEL FOR PREDICTING THE PERFORMANCE OF PHOTOVOLTAIC SOLAR PANELS USING MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

The energy sector is currently changing towards renewable energy, such as photovoltaic solar, to the detriment of traditional fossil fuels. This growth is driven by the need to reduce greenhouse gas emissions. However, solar energy production has an inherent dependence on weather conditions. Indeed, increasing the ambient temperature beyond a certain threshold can lead to a significant reduction in the efficiency of photovoltaic cells. This phenomenon is linked to the increase in the electrical resistance of the semiconductor materials constituting the cells, which limits the circulation of electrical charges, thus compromising the production of electricity and reducing the efficiency of photovoltaic installations. The aim of this work is to contribute to the search for a model for predicting maximum powers in photovoltaic systems, using methods based on approaches offered in machine learning. This manuscript presents an analysis of the state functioning in photovoltaic cells under the effect of temperature's variations, linked to meteorological censuses over the last 45 years in six regions of North-West Algeria. A parametric study is carried out using the PVSyst software to indicate the significant impact of different factors on energy production. Next, an assessment of the prediction models is developed using machine learning. At the end of this study, two prediction models are compared and tested in order to satisfy the concordance and reliability of the results.

Index Terms: Photovoltaic Panels, Climate Change, Maximum Powers, Machine Learning, Prediction Models.

1. INTRODUCTION

Over the past few decades, photovoltaic (PV) technology has emerged as a key renewable energy source, experiencing significant global growth [1–3]. As the

deployment of PV systems continues to expand, ensuring their reliability and long-term availability has become increasingly critical [4–7]. Although PV panels typically have a lifespan of 20 to 25 years, their performance can deteriorate due to various environmental stressors encountered during operation [8–12].

A comprehensive review of the literature highlights that climate change—particularly the ongoing rise in global temperatures—is one of the major factors contributing to PV panel degradation [13–19]. In response, many researchers have focused on enhancing PV system efficiency despite the adverse impacts of such environmental conditions [20–22].

The primary objective of this study is to conduct a theoretical investigation aimed at developing a predictive model for estimating the maximum power output and overall performance of photovoltaic systems, specifically in the context of rising installation site temperatures driven by global warming.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Different and many researches have adopted various physical prediction and machine learning models to solve the problems related about temperature's effects on the degradation of operation in PV panels [23-30]. In general terms, the quality of performance and proper functioning of solar panels strongly depend on climate change. However, climate varies considerably from region to region, depending on specific weather conditions and extreme weather events such as storms, hurricanes and hail can physically damage solar panels, and therefore reduce their efficiency.

Climate change has a significant impact on the performance of photovoltaic panels [31-33]. Indeed, increasing temperature generally reduces the efficiency of solar panels and photovoltaic cells lose efficiency when the temperature exceeds a certain threshold around 25°C. The intensity and duration of solar radiation in certain regions can also be modified, the increase in radiation could seem beneficial, but an excessive increase can lead to more rapid degradation of the panels.

Other factors can also influence this performance, such as the orientation of the panels, their inclination, the quality of the installation as well as the accumulation of snow or dust on the panels causing a reduction in the quantity of sunlight that reaches the cells.

Currently, global warming represents one of the major issues and challenges for the solar energy sector. Recent years have seen an unprecedented increase in average global temperatures. However, technological advances and a better understanding of impacts make it possible to minimize these effects and guarantee the sustainability of photovoltaic installations.

Machine learning models are widely used due to their use of historical data that accurately reflects actual system performance. Additionally, these models can make predictions without the design parameters of the solar PV system.

The reliability of existing models, developed by hand researchers [34-42], marked a significant improvement in accuracy for predicting the output power of the solar PV system as well as the total yield and the performance ratio having error ratios the weakest based on the different algorithms.

Exploiting the capabilities of machine learning makes it more possible to create predictive models capable of estimating with great precision the performance of a PV solar panel based on the coefficient expressing the relationship between the reference temperature and the power maximum. More generally, the use of algorithms developed in machine learning [43] could often address challenges such as the complexity of interactions where the relationships between temperature and power are not linear and can be influenced by numerous other factors.

Most studies conducted on the use of machine learning to forecast solar PV production, have focused on specific time horizons such as one hour, one day and one month.

The contribution of this research is to develop a theoretical model allowing the prediction of the performances of photovoltaic systems such as efficiency and yield by assessing the variation in maximum powers under the effect of the increase in site temperature caused by climate changes over time.

3. METHODOLOGY

The process accepted for this research is characterized by the combination of the results of a parametric study with an analysis developed in machine learning.

3.1 Basic assumptions

The essential aim of carrying out a parametric study is to evaluate the different factors governing the efficiency and performance of photovoltaic systems.

The digital simulation of the related systems constitutes a very effective means for the realization of the various models. Our analysis is carried out using the commercial software PVsyst version 7.1.8, the different characteristics of the type of panel adopted for the study are summarized in the following table (Table 1).

Table 1 : Monocrystalline module features

Power (Watt)	Tension (Volt)	Length (mm)	Width (mm)	Thickness (mm)	Weight (Kg)	Surface (m ²)
250	26	1640	990	35	20	1.624

The parameters involved are affected by climate change based on temperature censuses recorded over a period of 45 years (1979 to 2023), in North-West Algeria. The regions considered are Maghnia, Relizane, Sidi Bel Abbès, Ain-Témouchent, Beni-Saf and Oran.

Geographic coordinates and the location of the planned site are fundamental data for the success of processes based on simulations of photovoltaic systems. The importance of this data lies not only in the sizing of the system and the estimation of energy production, but also in the study of shadow and for the calculation of solar irradiation in order to optimize the inclination and the orientation (Figure.1).

Figure 1: Trajectory of the sun (case of Maghnia)

Geographic coordinates provide also for access to local meteorological databases (irradiance, temperature..., etc.) which are essential for estimating the energy production of photovoltaic installation. Simulation models can take into account seasonal variations in sunlight and temperature, which have a direct impact on energy production.

Weather state is not uniform globally and affects some regions more than others. The climate of Algeria, and more particularly of the North-West, has experienced significant changes in recent decades. These changes are mainly attributed to global warming.

The graph illustrated in the following figure (Figure 2) shows that the variation in average annual temperature for the regions targeted by our study, where the effects of climate change are clearly visible in recent years.

Figure 2: Temperatures recorded during the period from 1979 to 2023 [44-49]

3.2 Parametric study

The results obtained from the parametric study are mainly oriented towards the analysis of the influence of the effect of the increase in the average annual temperature in the installation sites on the variation of that of the panels and consequently on maximum power and electrical production.

Figure 3: Factors influencing photovoltaic system performance

The graphs shown above (figure 3) come from the results extracted from the simulation of the monocrystalline photovoltaic system. The amount of solar energy received per unit area varies depending on geographic location, season and weather conditions. As mentioned previously, temperature directly affects panel performance where efficiency generally decreases with increasing temperature.

The exploitation of the data collected reveals the correlations between certain parameters, shown in the matrix found below (figure.4). The connection of the maximum power with the temperature of the photovoltaic cell is very direct and significant.

Figure 4: Correlation matrix between the different variables

4. DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

4.1 Impact of ambient temperature on panels

The visualization of statistics on the state of affairs in the region studied regarding climate change over time, as well as the observation of the results from the parametric study carried out previously, were the subject of an evaluation. more accurate and more precise to predict the phenomenon of lowering of maximum powers when the temperature increases.

Figure 4: Effect of ambient temperature on cell temperature.

The temperature of the air surrounding the solar panels has a direct and significant influence on the temperature of the photovoltaic cells (figure.4). Under normal conditions, the heat produced by cells must be dissipated to the environment; but if the ambient temperature is high, heat dissipation is less efficient and the cells reach higher temperatures.

4.2 Impact of temperature on maximum power

Temperature is a critical factor influencing the performance of solar panels. As the temperature increases, the maximum power of the panels decreases. This is called the temperature coefficient. In some cases, excessive temperatures can cause irreversible degradation of photovoltaic cells. A good understanding of the impact of this factor makes it possible to optimize the choice of equipment and installation to maximize electricity production.

The temperature coefficient indicates how much a panel's maximum power decreases for each degree Celsius above the reference temperature. This coefficient therefore affects the operating temperature of each solar panel.

According to figures shown below, the effect of temperature and incident irradiation on the current is less marked but there is a slight increase. Since power is the product of voltage times current, decreasing voltage outweighs increasing current, resulting in an overall drop in maximum power. Notably, the open-circuit voltage of PV cells decreases as temperature increases, which is the primary cause of the reduction in maximum power.

Figure 5: Variation of maximum power as a function of temperature and solar irradiation

4.3 Model of prediction using machine learning analysis

The integration of the tools adopted in machine learning in this investigation is appreciable given the complexity of the influential factors where the power produced by a photovoltaic cell depends on numerous variable and often correlated factors: solar irradiance, temperature, humidity, etc. The quantity of data provided and the dynamic adaptation of

the models to be trained may also be among the factors requiring a search for more robust and advanced methods to solve this type of problems.

Generally speaking, using machine learning can improve the prediction of the maximum power of photovoltaic cells. This prediction is essential to maximize the yield and optimize the operation of solar installations.

The observation of the results of the parametric study and the analysis of the data collected relating to the planned sites were subject to the application of a process based on the use of various machine learning algorithms.

Our analysis is carried out using V/S Code version 1.91.1 available in Python. This part of the work consists of a set of structured and well-connected steps:

- ✓ Creation of a database: Weather measurements and panel characteristics are collected, cleaned and prepared.
- ✓ Choice of an algorithm: Supervised learning algorithms are used to establish relationships between inputs (weather conditions, panel characteristics) and output (maximum power). Six algorithms are adopted to run this application: Linear Regression, Decision Tree, Random Forests, Gradient Boosting machine and Support Vector Machines (SVM).
- ✓ Model training: including adjusting the algorithm parameters and using the training set to learn the model parameters and then validating the model.
- ✓ Model evaluation: metrics and error analysis are used to compare different models for final optimization.

The involvement of artificial intelligence in optimization tools is increasingly suitable when looking for models to predict maximum electricity production under unfavourable external conditions. The transition to machine learning requires a well-defined set of variables called input variables in order to carry out the training. The model is trained on the training data to learn how to establish relationships between the input variables (temperature, irradiance, etc.) and the output variable (maximum power). Once validated, the model can be used to predict maximum power in real time based on current weather conditions.

The use of a multitude of machine learning algorithms led us to explore several variants for the selection of the optimal model. For the case of our study, six algorithms are deployed with a distribution of 80% of input variables intended for training and the remaining 20% are intended for validation. The models developed during this analysis are evaluated and compared in terms of measuring the mean square errors between the predicted values and the actual values (RMSE); and also by the coefficient of determination (R^2). This coefficient makes it possible to decisively evaluate the quality of a regression model.

Two variants are obtained; the first designates the single-parameter model and the second corresponds to the two-parameter model (Figures 6a and 6b).

Figure 6.a: TPM model results

Figure 6.b: OPM model results

The final examination of the results from this analysis leads to the deployment of the two-parameter model (TPM) for the prediction of the maximum powers of solar panels.

The following table (Table.2) summarizes the concordance of the results corresponding to the two variants of the selected models having an acceptable coefficient of determination (greater than 85%).

Table 2 : Summary of final results

Algorithm		Linear Regression	Rundom-Forest	Decision Tree	SVM	K-NN	G-Boost
Model							
OPM	R2%	88.278	92.424	92.263	81.623	90.513	92.350
	RMSE	0.04868	0.0391	0.0395	0.0609	0.0438	0.0393
TPM	R2%	92.352	95.415	95.333	80.172	94.951	95.308
	RMSE	0.0393	0.0304	0.0307	0.0633	0.0319	0.0308

The use of methods based on machine learning makes it possible to accurately predict the maximum power depending on the temperature and different factors, moreover, contributes to the optimization of all performances in order to achieve better use solar energy and a more efficient energy transition.

4. CONCLUSION

This study aims to optimize forecasting models for energy production and the performance of photovoltaic solar panels, focusing on power prediction under the continuous rise in temperature over the years.

In addition to the use of the tools offered by machine learning, the combination of the results from the parametric study by considering the influence of the temperature coefficient, and the visualization of the data combined with the climate history, constructs a essential and decisive approach for the development of prediction models. The evaluation of the tested models highlighted the need to choose solar panels adapted to climatic conditions.

The results of the comparisons carried out show that machine learning models can provide reliable long-term forecasts. This work opens up interesting perspectives for the integration of high-resolution meteorological data into forecast models, in order to further improve the precision of the estimates.

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